

**REQUESTED STATUS OF WORK PACKAGES
FOR REPORTING PERIOD 1 (From: 2022-06-01 – To: 2024-05-31)**

	Status of Completion	Completion %
WP1	Completed - RP1	100 %
WP2	Completed - RP1	100 %
WP3	Completed - RP1	100 %
WP4	Completed - RP1	100 %
WP5	Completed - RP1	100 %
WP6	Completed - RP1	100 %